

The Effect of Workplace Spirituality on Innovative Work Behaviour of Employees with Reference to Auto Mobile Sector in Tamilnadu

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ABSTRACT

Automobile sector is one of the recent technology in modern world today. Organization facing problem like conflicts in their interpersonal role, not satisfied employees, poor in trust. This study helps to manage these problems with the workplace spirituality and innovative behavior even though workplace spirituality is popular in recent years but success rate of workplace spirituality in various sectors is low especially lack of study in automobile sectors. To improve the organization environment top officials trying to implement many steps for the improvement which is said to be as workplace spirituality. Organization trying to make employees willingness to work for the creation of innovative ideas in an organization. In this study workplace spirituality focus towards inner life, meaningful work, sense of community, alignment with organizational values. This research reveals that presence of workplace spirituality which influence the innovative behavior. Questionnaire has been circulated to 110 middle level managers in automobile industries in Tamilnadu district. This results from the study shows the positive influence on innovative behavior in automobile industries and different analysis has been used such as reliability testing, descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis were used in this study.

1. Introduction

India is one of the fastest growing economy in the automobile manufacturing sector especially in southern part of India. i.e. Detroit of Asia. At the same time employment opportunities for the people those who all involved in automobile sectors and which automobile industries contributes 7.1% growth in the gross domestic product and also 27% growth in the industrial sector and India Exports more than 4.3 % and more than 8% of country in field of Research and Development. Already many researchers have done their research in the topic of workplace spirituality and still it has scope for more research with the combination of workplace spirituality with different variables such as innovative behavior and so. This is how in this study trying to study about the innovative behavior of individual with the workplace spirituality.

Many organization facing problem among the employees those who work as the machines and works for money oriented and to create the dynamic environment in the organization trying to implement the meaning and purpose of the life which leads to the workplace spirituality and the innovative measures can avoid the damages at workplace in both ways physical damages of the property and also the other work in the organization which helps to avoid the employees turnover and absenteeism and improve the working condition of the environment. Individual innovative behavior used as one of the variable and which the employees in an organization.

Employees in an organization which they can use their innovative skills at work place for the better productivity at the workplace and which it creates the affection on the organization and employees in an organization which perceives the surface of the environment where they can use their innovative ideas for

implementation in an organization. Innovative behavior and creativity act as the weapon for the organization which leads to the important implementation of ideas of the changes happen only through the innovative behavior organization showing more attention towards employee's knowledge which they can innovative ideas where employees can use their knowledge for innovation. Innovative behavior can be explained in different for such as idea generation, promotion, realization and applying ideas in the role of the work in the organization and also individual innovative behavior happens only when they interact with others organization believes in that formula.

Workplace spirituality plays important role in innovation which meaningful work creates the effects on the ideas which it leads to the innovative projects. In the modern competitive world to accomplish simple task in the organization innovative action is required in their own job for thinking which pays ways for the innovation. Every levels in the organization is required innovation for multifunctional to follow and implement the innovative ideas. To extract the new innovative ideas from individuals in an organization they has to give full freedom for the speech of employees in an organization which pays ways for innovative ideas for building up of the better environment . Organization has the provide openness to express the employees which the innovative ideas will come up in the minds of the employees.

2. Literature Review

Elkins (1990) Workplace spirituality is about experiencing awareness of different values such as inner self, life ,nature etc. the main purpose of the workplace spirituality is to identify their purpose of life with meaning full work at work place in altruism, to know the meaningful fruits of workplace spirituality.

Ashmos & Duchon (2000) explained about the workplace spirituality that recognizes individuals or employees findings one's spirit towards work which is acknowledging and meaningful work with professionally with its own power leads to the productive work life and also contributes to the society with meaningful work.

Moxley (2000) explained about every aspects of work and life are profound towards interaction and people communicate towards all aspects at workplace this leads to the psychological effects in the minds of employees through metaphysical reality at workplace.

Milliman (1994) research is about the relationship between innovative behavior with the workplace spirituality has the positive relationship with the creating ideas and satisfaction and also it creates the spirituality among the employees and promotes the team's performance which leads boosting the employees morale in an organization.

Turner (1999) research studies about the employee perception at workplace which leads to the financial success and individual creative and innovative ideas which is effective for the organization goals and the employees in an organization feel satisfied with their work at workplace and this will leads to employee commitment in the workplace and also it helps to create the organizational climate and culture.

Buarack (1999) research studies is all about the internal and external things of the employees in an organization creates the impact through creativity and innovation which leads to the trust of the environment and commitment towards the work which the employees in the organization for their improvement in their employee performance happens only through spirituality with their attitudes and the continuous performance and responsibilities towards the society.

Khanifer et.al (2010) studies about the investigation with the relationship with workplace spirituality with the commitment and creativity which is positively correlated with other variables and which the spirituality helps to improve the organization efficiency through the creativity ideas and it helps to achieve the goals of the organization.

Sender (2003) workplace spirituality research done by them and explained about the encouragement commitment, spirituality towards the innovation of employees by serving the effective work at workplace through their individuality skills with creativity and innovative skills which is positively correlates with innovation and the commitment towards the work.

Badrinarayanan (2008) research is about the spirituality at workplace and the innovation of which the employees in an organization has its voluntary and the behavior of the employees at workplace which has its uncertainty and effort of employees has the impact on the organization success through the innovation with the spirituality creates the financial success.

Dehoff S (1998) research is about the study of psychological growth in the minds of employees in an organization through its spirit of individuals and the contribution through the human growth to be perceived and highest level through the self-

actualization which theory of workplace helps the organization for their growth and expansion.

3. Research Methodology

A. Research question

Do the workplace spirituality effects contribute individual innovative behavior?

B. Research objectives

To assess the influence of workplace spirituality with individual innovative behavior

C. Research design:

The study is basically descriptive in nature. The employees at manufacturing sector were encouraged to complete the process of filling up questionnaire of workplace spirituality. Questionnaire has been circulated to 150 employees in automobile manufacturing sectors and finally 110 filled questionnaire has been collected from employees. The data has been collected from the employees of automobile manufacturing sector in Tamilnadu. A questionnaire with 15 items developed to assess the impact of workplace spirituality on manufacturing sector.

The main purpose of the study is the uniqueness with the variables combination discussed with the experts panel and time spend with the experts and make them participate with the discussion for constructing the questionnaire.

The purpose of this study is to introduce the 4 instruments to measure the impact on the individual innovative behavior usefulness of the workplace spirituality for developing the work spirit and creates the good relationship between individuals and the management with different variables in an organization. 15 items has been used in this study to measure the construct the individual innovative behavior. The participant's has been given by us about 51 items has been used with the 5 point likert scale from the following scaling strongly agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and strongly disagree for Strongly agree (5) Agree (4) Neutral (3) Disagree (2) Strongly Disagree (1)

4. Analysis and Discussion

Table 1: Reliability Analysis
Cronbach's Alpha used for checking the reliability of the study

S.no	Name of the construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
1	Inner life	0.86	5
2	Meaningful at work	0.92	10
3	Sense of community	0.80	15
4	Alignment with organizational values	0.95	8
5	Innovative behavior	0.91	10
Total number of items			48

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that alpha score for inner life is about 0.86 with 5 items, meaningful at work 0.92 with 10 items, sense of community with 0.80 with 15 items, Alignment with organization values of 0.95 with 10 items, innovative behavior of 0.91 with 10 items.

Table II Descriptive Statistics

S.no	Name of the construct	Mean score	Standard Deviation
1	Inner life	3.5742	0.61347
2	Meaningful at work	3.8823	0.72239
3	Sense of community	3.7453	0.71899
4	Alignment with organizational values	3.6391	0.67765
5	Innovative behavior	3.2234	0.67765

Inference:

Inner life has been tested with 5 items with is construct for inner life. The average scoring done with the inner life with 5 items is 3.5742 which shows that inner life of the employees in an organization is unique with the content overall agree with the variables and the meaningful at work with the 3.8823 and sense of community with 3.7453 and alignment with organizational values with 3.6391 and the innovative behavior with 3.2234.

Table III correlation

	Inner life	Meaningful at work	Sense of Community	Alignment with organization values
Inner life	1	0.733**	0.765**	0.735**
Meaningful at work	0.733**	1	0.755**	0.610**
Sense of community	0.765**	0.755**	1	0.579**
Alignment with organizational values	0.735**	0.610**	0.579**	1
Innovative behaviour	0.766**	0.712**	0.669**	0.651**

*significant at the 0.05 level (2 tailed)

**significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)

Inference:

The table above shows that correlation between variables with the individual innovative behavior .It is stated that correlation significant level at 1% 2 tailed the development variables individual innovative behavior is positive correlated

with the independent variables such as inner life, meaningful work, alignment with organizational values, and sense of community.

Table IV Regression analysis
Regression analysis
Dependent variable : Innovative Behavior

Variable	Unstandardized coefficient	Standardized coefficient	t	sig
	B	Std.Error	Beta	
Inner life	-0.493	0.563	-.319	0.403
Meaningful at work	-0.304	0.144	-.388	0.74
Sense of community	0.399	0.133	0.499	0.14
Alignment with organizational values	0.510	0.201	0.310	0.16
R	0.783	0.210		.022
R ²	0.66			
Std Error of the estimate	0.43111			

Inference :

R value from the above table is about the coefficient of correlation. This has higher degree of correlation. R2 refers about the value with the determination of the co-efficient. It is about the 61% with the dependent variable is the greater variable. From the above table it is found that the variables from independent has inner life, meaningful at work , sense of community , alignment of values provides maximum contributed to the individual and innovative behavior.

5. Conclusion

Workplace spirituality is major solution to reduce the employee turnover and absenteeism . It is also evident that the employees in an organization will never go down from this study researchers reveals about that workplace spirituality plays vital role and brings the creative and innovative role in an organization . Providing the enough space for discussion and introduce the forum facilities coming development in an organization .

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